

Effect Of Hydro-Alcoholic Root Extract of *Nyctanthes Arborescens* Ointment on Wound Healing Potential on Wistar Albino Rats

Debananda Champatisingh*, Ranjit Mohapatra

University Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Department of Pharmacology, Utkal University, Vani Vihar, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this current exploration was for screening the wound healing potential of hydro-alcoholic root extract of plant *Nyctanthes arborescens*. *Nyctanthes arborescens* (Oleaceae), a most common medicinal plant in traditional Indian medicine. According to folk of medicine and experimental data raised an outlook on this plant for evaluating wound healing potential. Hydro-alcoholic root extract of *Nyctanthes arborescens* (HARNA) has been examined for its wound healing activity by utilizing wound healing model in albino rats: (i) excision wound model following application of standard (Soframycin) and text extract ointments topically. Animals have been categorized into 4 groups with 6 animals in every group. Group I treated with simple ointment base, Group II treated with standard Soframycin 5% w/w ointment, Group III and IV treated with HARNA 5% w/w and 10% w/w ointments respectively. Results obtained upon treatment with the plant extract groups shown activity close to standard drug activity, Soframycin, in terms of wound contraction ability, time taken for wound closure and period of epithelialization. 10% w/w HARNA ointment has produced better wound healing potential after comparing to 5% w/w HARNA ointment. The obtained results notified that *Nyctanthes arborescens* swifts the wound healing process by reducing wound's surface area and enhancing hydroxyproline content.

Keywords: Wound healing potential, *Nyctanthes arborescens* Linn., Excision wound model, Hydro-alcoholic root extract ointment, Soframycin, Wistar albino rat.

INTRODUCTION

Wounds are physical, chemical or thermal breaks in the normal continuity of skin or its underlying tissue leading to disruption of their anatomical and functional integrity [1]. An intricate natural process in which the skin or tissue repairs itself after injury, the wound healing, is governed by various phases namely; hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, tissue remodeling or resolution and maturation [2]. These phases, in the complex and dynamic process, of wound healing involve a cascade of cellular and biochemical events mediated by various cytokines, growth factors and enzymes [3].

Wounds are still a major problem in developing countries, often leading to serious complications [4] because their care is complex, time consuming, sometimes confusing, and almost always expensive

[5]. Although, various therapeutic regimens involving antibiotics, analgesics and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs are available for the management of wound, majority of these therapies are not devoid of the numerous unwanted side effects [6].

Nyctanthes arborescens is a value aided medicinal plant belongs to Oleaceae family. The plant generally grows in tropical and subtropical regions. It commonly known as Night jasmine, Harsinghar & Parijat. It is a common wild hardy large shrub or small tree. Different parts of this plant are used in Indian systems of medicine for various pharmacological actions like as anti-leishmaniasis [7], anti-viral [8], anti-fungal [9], anti-pyretic [10], anti-histaminic [11], anti-malarial [12], mast cell stabilizer [13], anti-oxidant [14], anti-inflammatory [15] and many more activities. In the present study, we designed a method

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

to evaluate the wound healing potential of roots of *N. arbortristis* using excision wound model in wistar albino rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Plant Material and Plant Extraction:

Fresh and mature plant roots of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* Linn. has been collected in bulk quantities from the medicinal garden at U.D.P.S and Chandaka Forest, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India. The plant specimen was authenticated by IMMT, BBSR, Odisha, India. The voucher specimen of *N. arbortristis* Linn. (Voucher No. IMMT-134/22) have been preserved in the institution herbarium of U.D.P.S, Bhubaneswar for future reference.

The dried parts (root) was then grated to coarse powder by mechanical grinder and allowed to extract with hydro-alcohol (water 30: ethanol 70) in Soxhlet's apparatus. The crude extracts were evaporated to dryness under vacuum and placed it in vacuum desiccator for further drying. Preliminary phytochemical investigation was performed and on the eve of the phytochemicals of hydro-alcoholic root extracts of *N. arbortristis* (HARNA) was selected for wound healing screening in albino rats. The herbal ointment was prepared by levigation method.

Animals: Wistar albino rats weighing 150-200 g were used for the present study. All animals were maintained in the animal house of Dadhichi College of Pharmacy, Cuttack, Odisha, under controlled conditions of temperature $25 \pm 2^\circ \text{C}$, relative humidity 55-60 %, and 12-h light-dark cycles for experimental purposes. They are grouped into experimental and control groups, kept in polypropylene cages with sterile paddy husk as bedding and free access to standard pellets to feed and water *ad libitum*. All the studies conducted were approved by the Institutional Animal Ethical Committee (IAEC) of Dadhichi College of Pharmacy, Sundargram, Cuttack, Odisha (Approval No. -1200/PO/Re/S/08/CCSEA).

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN:

All the rats had been anaesthetized utilizing slight vapour inhalation of diethyl ether. The rats have been categorized into 4 main groups ($n=6$) as shown in Table 1. Animals have been bared before wounding at dorsal thoracic areas.

Table 1: Experimental design of excision wound model

Groups	Treatment	Dose (applied topically/day)
I	Wound control	Simple ointment base
II	Positive control	Standard Soframycin (5% w/w) ointment
III	HARNA 5% ointment	HARNA (5% w/w) ointment
IV	HARNA 10% ointment	HARNA (10% w/w) ointment

Excision Wound Model: Excision wound was made on the depilated region of the skin. A standardized wound area was marked on the dorsal surface of the desensitized rats and skin in full thickness was ablated to obtain a wound area of about 500 mm² diameters. Homeostasis was attained by blotting the ulcerated area with cotton swab dipped in normal saline. The entire wound was left open. The wound diameter was measured using calipers on alternate days and the epithelialization period recorded at the end of the study. Number of days required for falling of the scar without any residual raw wound gave the period of epithelialization. It was measured in days from wounding day (day zero) till the full epithelialization. The wound area was measured with a translucent paper and traced the epithelialization period. The wound area of each animal was measured on days 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 16 and 20 after inflicting the wound [16].

The following parameters i.e., wound size reduction, percentage of wound contraction, period of epithelialization, hydroxyproline contents were recorded on post wounding days.

Measurement of Wound Closure: The rate of wound closure has been analyzed by tracing the wound on 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 16 and 20 post wounding days utilizing permanent marker and transparent paper and noticed wound regions were calculated utilizing 1 mm² scale of graph paper. The wound contraction progress was evaluated by using the following formula;

$$\% \text{ Wound contraction} = \frac{\text{Initial wound size} - \text{specific day wound size}}{\text{Initial wound area}} \times 100$$

Measurement of Period of Epithelialization: Wound falling with no raw scab behind has been

considered as perfect epithelialization and the days in number needed for was noticed as period of epithelialization [17].

At the end of the study, on 20th day, biochemical parameter like hydroxyproline content was determined from excised granulation tissue [18].

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

All data were expressed as mean \pm SD (n=6). Statistical analysis was performed at $p < 0.05$ to $p < 0.01$ between the groups by one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA) followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test using Graph Pad prism software (version 10).

RESULTS:

The intricate cellular process of wound healing allows damaged tissue to return as nearly to its pre-damaged state as feasible. The type and degree of damage, the tissues overall health and its capacity for repair all influence the healing process. The standard Soframycin serves as a common benchmark for evaluating the medicinal efficacy in comparison with the crude medication and the control. Animals in the

extract and conventional treatment groups showed a significant reduction in the epithelialization period and an increase in the pace of wound contraction.

Wound Contraction: Topical application of hydro-alcoholic root extract of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* (HARNA) 5% and 10% w/w ointments showed effect on the process of wound healing on the rats. The progress size reduction of wound area was shown in Table 2 and Figure 1 as well as the percentage of wound contraction induced by treatment of HARNA 5% and 10% w/w ointments, control and Soframycin 5% w/w skin ointment were shown in Table 3 and Figure 2. The HARNA 10% w/w ointment treated group shown noticeable wound size reduction from the six day of treatment and with highly significant difference were seen from 12th day onwards in comparison with the control group. But the percentage of wound contraction was observed nearly same with the standard, Soframycin. The rate of wound size reduction of 5% w/w and 10% w/w HARNA started from the 12th day and 6th day onwards with the control group respectively. The standard drug, Soframycin 5%w/w ointment showed the rate of wound reduction from 6th day onwards with respect to control group.

Table 2: Effect of hydro-alcoholic root extract of *Nyctanthes Arbortristis* (HARNA) ointment on wound size reduction (mm²) on different groups of animal in excision wound model

Post wound healing (Days)	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV
0	501.2 \pm 1.47	508.4 \pm 1.18	505.6 \pm 2.05	502.2 \pm 1.72
3	478.4 \pm 1.49	428.8 \pm 1.11	480.2 \pm 1.47	430.4 \pm 1.85
6	402.8 \pm 2.78	301.4 \pm 1.86*	409.2 \pm 1.16	300.2 \pm 1.72*
9	318.2 \pm 1.16	218.2 \pm 1.68*	378.8 \pm 1.16	209.4 \pm 1.85*
12	230.2 \pm 0.74	101.2 \pm 2.03*	198.6 \pm 1.85	98.2 \pm 2.04*
16	108.4 \pm 1.96	40.4 \pm 1.37**	94.6 \pm 1.02*	38.2 \pm 1.72**
20	42.6 \pm 2.05	0	37.8 \pm 1.16	0

Values are expressed as mean \pm SD, n=6. Using Tukey's multiple comparison test, the intergroup variation between various groups was conducted by graph pad Prism software & Data were analyzed by using one way analysis of variances (ANOVA). ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ when compared to control group; one way ANOVA.

Figure 1: wound size reduction (mm²) of HARNA ointment on different groups of animal in excision wound model

Table 3: Effect of hydro-alcoholic root extract of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* (HARNA) ointment on percentage of wound contraction (%) on different groups of animal in excision wound model

Post wound healing (Days)	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV
0	0	0	0	0
3	4.5	15.6	5.1	14.2
6	19.6	40.7	19.1	40.2
9	36.5	57.1*	25.1	58.3*
12	54.1	80.1**	60.7	80.4**
16	78.3	92.1**	81.2*	92.4**
20	91.5	100**	92.5*	100**

Values are expressed as mean ± SD, n=6. Using Tukey’s multiple comparison test, the intergroup variation between various groups was conducted by graph pad Prism software & Data were analyzed by using one way analysis of variances (ANOVA). **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05 when compared to control group; one way ANOVA.

Figure 2: Percentage of wound contraction (%) and period of epithelization of HARNA ointment on post wounding days

Epithelialization Period: The time required for complete epithelialization of the excision wound is an important parameter to assess the wound healing process. It has been noticed during the study. The

extract treated groups show less mean time as comparable with the control group and found no significant difference (10% w/w HARNA) with the standard group as shown in Table 4 and Figure 2.

Table 4: Effect of hydro-alcoholic root extract of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* (HARNA) ointment on period of epithelialization (no. of days)

Groups	Period of epithelization (days)
I	23.33 ± 1.52
II	12.57 ± 0.57**
III	21.53 ± 0.57
IV	13.53 ± 1.00**

Values are expressed as mean ± SD, n=6. Using Tukey’s multiple comparison test, the intergroup variation between various groups was conducted by graph pad Prism software & Data were analyzed by using one way analysis of variances (ANOVA). **p

< 0.01, when compared to control group; one way ANOVA.

Hydroxyproline Content: Hydroxyproline, an amino acid, is the major component of collagen which provides strength and support to the tissues. Collagen is a major protein of the extracellular matrix and is the major component that ultimately contributes to wound strength. Breakdown of collagen liberates free hydroxyproline and its peptides. Measurement of the hydroxyproline could be used as an index for collagen turnover [19]. The hydroxyproline content was increased significantly in dose dependent manner by 10% HARNA and standard Soframycin treated groups as shown in Table 5 and Figure 3.

Table 5: Effect of hydro-alcoholic root extract of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* (HARNA) ointment on biochemical parameters

Groups/Treatment	Hydroxyproline ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ tissue)
Group-I (control)	0.62 \pm 0.049
Group-II (Standard)	0.74 \pm 0.049**
Group-III (HARNA 5% w/w)	0.65 \pm 0.049*
Group-IV (HARNA 10% w/w)	0.71 \pm 0.024**

Values are expressed as mean \pm SD, n=6. Using Tukey's multiple comparison test, the intergroup variation between various groups was conducted by graph pad Prism software & Data were analyzed by using one way analysis of variances (ANOVA). **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05 when compared to control group; one way ANOVA.

Effect of HARNA ointment on hydroxyproline content of excised wound in rats

Figure 3: Effect of HARNA ointment on hydroxyproline content of excised wound in rats

DISCUSSION

Wound is a major problem of health in relation to morbidity and mortality. It involved in wound healing are epithelialization, contraction and connective tissue deposition. It depends on regulated biosynthesis and deposition of new collagens and their subsequent maturation [20]. In the tissue repair process, inflammatory cells which synthesize extracellular matrices including collagen and keratinocytes for reepithelialization of wound tissues [21]. It is a complex process of restoring cellular structures and tissue layers in damaged tissue together to its normal state and commencing in the fibroblastic stage where the area of the wound undergoes shrinkage [22]. It comprises of different phases such as contraction, granulation, epithelization and collagenation [23, 24].

Studies were revealed that flavonoids are also known to promote the wound healing process mainly due to their astringent and antimicrobial properties which appear to be responsible for the wound healing and increased rate of epithelialisation [25]. Similar types of wound-healing activity were reported on *Vernonia arborea* [26] and *Pentas lanceolata* [27].

Collagen is a major protein of the extracellular matrix and is the major component that ultimately contributes to wound strength [28]. Breakdown of collagen liberates free hydroxyproline and its peptides. Measurement of the hydroxyproline could be used as an index for collagen turnover [29]. Hydroxyproline, an amino acid, is the major component of collagen which provides strength and support to the tissues. The liberation of hydroxyproline may be due to collagen breakdown. Hence its measurement can be used as an index for collagen turnover as well as a biochemical marker for tissue collagen [30].

CONCLUSION

In this research work, hydro-alcoholic root extract of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* plant was examined for its wound healing activity in excision wound model in rats. Hydro-alcoholic extract of the plant material proved its significant potentials against wound healing. The results were also comparable to those of a standard drug, Soframycin, in terms of wound size reduction, percentage of wound contraction, days of epithelialization and improvement of hydroxyproline content during the experimental period in excision

wounding in wistar albino rats. So this plant may contain the phytoconstituents or chemicals those potentially act on the biological systems and prove the wound healing potentials by various mechanism on the affected wound sites.

REFERENCES

1. Tsala OE, Amadou D, Habtemarian S. Natural wound healing and bioactive natural products. *Phytopharmacol.* 2013;4:532-560.
2. Premarathna AD, Ranaheva TH, Wijesekera SK, Harishchandra DL, Karunathilake KJK, Waduge RN, Wijesundara RRMKK, Jayasooriya AP, Wijewardana V, Rajapakse RPVJ. Preliminary screening of the aqueous extracts of twenty-three different seaweed species in Sri-Lanka with in-vitro and in-vivo assays. *Heliyon.* 2020;6(6):1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e03918>.
3. Dorjsembe B, Lee HJ, Kim M, Dulamjav B, Jigjid T, Nho CW. Achillea asiatica extract and its active compounds induce cutaneous wound healing. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 2017;206:306-314.
4. Strecker-McGraw MK, Jones TR, Baer DG. Soft Tissue Wounds and Principles of Healing. *Emergency Medicine Clinics of North America.* 2007;25:1-22.
5. Robson V, Dodd S, Thomas S. Standardized antibacterial honey (Medihoney™) with standard therapy in wound care: randomized clinical trial. *Journal of Advanced Nursing.* 2009;65:565-575.
6. Nagar HK, Srivastava AK, Srivastava R, Kurmi ML, Chandel HS, Ranawat MS. Pharmacological investigation of the wound healing activity of *Cestrum nocturnum* (L.) ointment in Wistar albino rats. *J. Pharm.* 2016;2(490):40-48.
7. Tandon JS, Srivastava V, Guru PY. Iridoids: A new class of leishmanicidal agents from *Nyctanthes arbortristis*. *J Nat Prod.* 1991;4:1102-1104.
8. Gupta P, Bajpai SK, Chandra K, Singh KL, Tandon JS. Antiviral profile of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* L. against encephalitis causing viruses. *Indian J Exp Biol.* 2005;43:1156-60.
9. Mishra RK, Mishra V, Pandey A, Tiwari AK, Pandey H, Sharma S, Pandey AC, Dikshit A. Exploration of anti-malassezia potential of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* L. and their application to combat the infection caused by *Mala s1* a novel allergen. *BMC Complement Altern Med.* 2016;16(1):1-14.
10. Saxena RS, Gupta B, Saxena KK, Srivastava VK, Prasad DN. Analgesic, antipyretic and ulcerogenic activity of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* leaf extract. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 1987;19(2):193-200.
11. Saxena RS, Gupta B, Lata S. Tranquilizing, antihistaminic and purgative activity of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* leaf extract. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 2002;81:321-25.
12. Simonsen HT, Nordskjold JB, Smitt UW, Nyman U, Palpu P, Joshi P, Varughese G. In vitro screening of Indian medicinal plants for antiparasmodial activity. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 2001;74(2):195-204.
13. Nirmal SA, Pal SC, Mandal SC. Mast cell stabilizing and bronchodilatory activity of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* bark. *Phytother. Res.* 2012;2(1):234-42.
14. Amarite O, Bhuskat P, Patel N, Gadgoli C. Evaluation of antioxidant activity of carotenoid from *Nyctanthes arbortristis*. *Int J Pharmacol Biol Sci.* 2007;2:57-59.
15. Omkar A, Jeeja T, Chhaya G. Evaluation of anti-inflammatory activity of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* and *Onosma echinodes*. *Pharmacog. Mag.* 2006;8:258-60.
16. Morton JJ, Malone MH. Evaluation of vulnerary activity by an open wound procedure in rats. *Archives of Internationales de Pharmacodynamie Therapie.* 1972;196:117-26.
17. Wilkinson HN, Hardman MJ. Wound healing: cellular mechanisms and pathological outcomes. *Open Biology.* 2023;10:200223. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsob.200223>.
18. Nayak PS, Das PK, Sahoo S, Sethi R, Nayak S, Joshi A. Phytochemical and Pharmacological Investigation of the Protective Effect of Plant *Hyptis suaveolens* against Duodenal Ulceration. *Journal of Global Pharma Technology.* 2009;1(1):82-87.
19. Sasidharan S, Logeswaran S, Latha LY. Wound healing activity of *Elaeis guineensis* leaf extract ointment. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 2012;13:336-347.
20. Agarwal PK, Singh A, Gaurav K, Goel S, Khanna HD, Goel RK. Evaluation of wound healing activity of extracts of plantain banana (*Musa*

- sapientum var. paradisiaca) in rats. Indian Journal of Experimental Biology. 2009;47(1):32–40.
21. Clark RAF. Cutaneous wound repair. In Physiology, Biochemistry and Molecular Biology of the Skin, L. A. Goldsmith, Ed. Oxford Press, Oxford, UK, 1991. pp. 576–601.
22. Chitra S, Patil MB, Ravi K. Wound healing activity of Hyptis suaveolens (L) poit (Lamiaceae). Int J Pharm Technol Res. 2009;1:737-744.
23. Ayyanar M, Ignacimuthu S. Herbal medicines for wound healing among tribal people in Southern India: ethnobotanical and scientific evidences. Int J Appl Res Nat Prod. 2009;2:29-42.
24. Wild T, Rahbarnia A, Kellner M, Sobotka L, Eberlein T. Basics in nutrition and wound healing. Nutrition. 2010;26:862-866.
25. Tsuchiya H, Sato M, Miyazaki T, Fujiwara S, Tanigaki S, Ohyama M, Tanaka T, Iinuma M. Comparative study on the antibacterial activity of phytochemical flavanones against methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus. J. Ethnopharmacol. 1996;50:27-34.
26. Manjunatha BK, Vidya SM, Rashmi KV, Mankani KL, Shilpa HJ, Singh S, Jagadeesh D. Evaluation of woundhealing potency of Vernonia arborea Hk. Indian J. Pharmacol. 2005;37:223-226.
27. Nayak BS, Vinutha B, Geetha B, Sudha B. Experimental evaluation of Pentas lanceolata for wound healing activity in rats. Fitotherapia. 2005;76:671-675.
28. Pattnaik S, Pattnaik B. A study of Lantana camara Linn aromatic oil as an antibacterial agent. International Journal of Pharma Sciences. 2010;1:32-35.
29. Sasidharan S, Logeswaran S, Latha LY. Wound healing activity of Elaeis guineensis leaf extract ointment. Int. J. Mol. Sci. 2012;13:336-347.
30. Nayak PS, Das PK, Sahoo S, Sethi R, Nayak S, Joshi A. Phytochemical and Pharmacological Investigation of the Protective Effect of Plant Hyptis Suaveolens against Duodenal Ulceration. Journal of Global Pharma Technology. 2009;1(1):82-87.

HOW TO CITE: Debananda Champatisingh*, Ranjit Mohapatra, Effect Of Hydro-Alcoholic Root Extract of Nyctanthes Arbotristis Ointment on Wound Healing Potential on Wistar Albino Rats, J. Pharm. Sci., 2025, 1 (11), 214-220. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17512372>

